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*ENTREPRENEURIAL EDUCATION: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF
BRAZILIAN THESES IN THE LAST YEARS¹*

**EDUCAÇÃO EMPREENDEDORA: UMA ANÁLISE BIBLIOMÉTRICA DE
TESES BRASILEIRAS NOS ÚLTIMOS ANOS**

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ABSTRACT

The research aimed to compile a bibliographic portfolio on the topic of 'Entrepreneurial Education.' Seventeen theses focused on the topic were identified. The bibliometric analysis revealed the main programs and base titles of each thesis. The universities, the temporal evolution of the publications, and the sources used were also analyzed. The titles with the highest citation on the topic included 'Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes,' 'Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology,' and 'Introduction to Information Retrieval.' Among the programs, Business Administration was the most recurrent. The research aims to contribute to the theoretical knowledge of 'Entrepreneurial Education' and provides a relevant database in the field. However, a limitation was the exclusive use of the Google Scholar (GS) database. It is recommended that future research explore other databases, keep the survey updated periodically, and use a more systematic approach to obtain the results.

Keywords: entrepreneurial education, entrepreneur, entrepreneurship, innovation.

¹ Recebido em 15/07/2024. Aprovado em 07/09/2024. DOI: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17209219

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RESUMO

A pesquisa teve como objetivo reunir um portfólio bibliográfico sobre o tema "Educação Empreendedora". Foram identificadas 17 teses direcionadas ao tema. A análise bibliométrica revelou os principais programas e títulos base de cada tese. Também foram analisadas as universidades, a evolução temporal das publicações e as fontes utilizadas. Os títulos que tiveram maior citação sobre o tema incluíram a formação social da mente: o desenvolvimento dos processos psicológicos superiores, Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology, Introduction to information retrieval. Dentre os programas, Administração foi o mais recorrente. A pesquisa buscou contribuir para o conhecimento teórico sobre "Educação Empreendedora" e fornece uma base de dados relevante na área. No entanto, uma limitação foi o uso exclusivo da base de dados do Google Scholar (GS). Recomenda-se que futuras pesquisas explorem outras bases de dados, mantenham o levantamento atualizado periodicamente e usem uma abordagem mais sistemática para obter os resultados.

Palavras-chave: educação empreendedora, empreendedor, empreendedorismo, inovação.

INTRODUCTION

The figure of the entrepreneur is associated by Schumpeter (1982) with the one who innovates and consequently brings forth the ability to emphasize and explain economic development. Therefore, entrepreneurship can be understood as the art of making things happen through creativity and motivation, thus consisting in the pleasure of innovating in any personal or organizational project, in spite of the opportunities and risks of the market and the social sphere (Baggio, 2014). According to Barreto (1998), entrepreneurship is a kind of skill in which something is created and/or established from very little or almost nothing, with, for example, the development of an organization representing a type of opposition to merely observing, analyzing, or describing it. This perspective fits perfectly into the work of Magalhães, Ramos, and Bezerra (2024), who investigate how rural

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entrepreneurship and family farming contribute to sustainable approaches in the rural environment.

From Zarpellon's perspective (2010, p. 48), the act of undertaking can be seen as a phenomenon directly linked to the creation of businesses, both through the emergence of opportunities and the need for survival, as well as through the occurrence of a social phenomenon capable of leading an individual or a given community to develop a series of abilities to solve problems and seek the development of their own future, thereby generating social and human capital. As an example, the theoretical framework used by Soares, Singh, and Borges (2024) is highlighted, as they explore, identify, and seize entrepreneurial opportunities in the coffee sector in the states of São Paulo and Minas Gerais, from the perspective of four entrepreneurs in the sector.

However, regardless of the conception adopted to define and describe entrepreneurship and its respective function, if the entrepreneurial process is an integral part of socioeconomic transformations, it is logical to assume that societies with more individuals possessing entrepreneurial attributes and characteristics are in a more favorable position to progress economically compared to those with fewer such individuals. Because of this, calls for entrepreneurial education are increasingly growing (Ndofrepi, 2020).

With the growing demand for entrepreneurial education, the academic environment provides a series of bibliographic studies directly focused on the theme of entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial education. Albano and Vasconcelos (2023) conduct a bibliometric study aimed at presenting and describing an overview of projects developed with a focus on entrepreneurship and innovation themes at a federal university. Meanwhile, Vilas Boas and Nascimento (2020) seek to understand the stage of research on Entrepreneurial Education and how it is structured from an intellectual and conceptual point of view based on a bibliography published in 2020.

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Nevertheless, there are no scientific works that indicate the choice of topics in doctoral theses produced in Brazil. From this perspective, the following research problem arises: do Brazilian doctoral theses from the past five years address entrepreneurial education? To this end, the general objective is defined as examining the panorama of Brazilian theses on Entrepreneurial Education over the past five years through a bibliometric analysis, with the purpose of identifying the main universities, programs, temporal evolution of publications, and the most cited sources. As a contribution of this research, the relationship between innovation and economic development is highlighted. Based on Schumpeter's (1982) ideas, the study reinforces the view that the entrepreneur is the one who innovates, driving economic development.

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION OVER THE YEARS

The term "entrepreneurial education" can encompass a diverse range of concepts, approaches, and perspectives. Thus, educating entrepreneurially emphasizes the personal development of learners through the cultivation of attitudes, skills, and values that strengthen entrepreneurial personalities (Fowler, 1997; Lopes, 2010; Kirby & Ibrahim, 2011; Gerba, 2012). In this way, entrepreneurial education seeks not only to promote behavioral and cognitive changes but also to drive the personal development of the aspiring entrepreneur in a broad sense (Gedeon, 2014; Leiva, Monge & Alegre, 2014; Rabelo, 2021).

The process of educating entrepreneurially may be seen either as a pedagogical program and organizational form or as a methodology and set of strategic activities, as discussed by Dolabela (1999), Andrade and Torkomian (2001), and Lopes (2010). This educational approach aims to provide knowledge and influence the processes of entrepreneurial intention (Jones and English, 2004; Liñán, 2004; Leiva, Monge and Alegre, 2014).

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Thus, conceptualizing entrepreneurial education has historically evolved over the past decades, reflecting a variety of theoretical and practical perspectives. Initially, Andrade, Vieira and Torkomian (2010) observed the diversity of interpretations regarding educational entrepreneurship, stressing the need for theoretical consistency in presenting these concepts. Monteiro (2020) highlights the innovative nature of entrepreneurial education, emphasizing its focus on active student participation, autonomy, and responsibility, in addition to entrepreneurial skills.

Fayolle, Gailly and Clerc-Lassas (2006) broaden this scope by considering any pedagogical program designed to develop entrepreneurial attitudes. It is worth noting that there is no specific diagnostic profile of students predisposed to learn about entrepreneurial education (Duarte and Costa, 2023). Lopes (2010) highlights its dynamic nature of transforming experience and knowledge into functional learning.

The analysis of various authors reveals different approaches to entrepreneurial education. Fowler (1997) views it as a means of developing entrepreneurial attributes aimed at social well-being. Dolabela (1999) describes it as a stimulus for students to become protagonists of their own lives, turning dreams into reality through strategies and choices. Andrade and Torkomian (2001) stress its role in human development, identifying and seizing opportunities to generate social and financial value.

Coan (2011) emphasizes the dynamic and social aspect of entrepreneurial education, where individuals identify opportunities for innovation. Bagheri and Pihie (2011) see it as a social process of interaction and reflection. Kirby and Ibrahm (2011) highlight the importance of changing students' thinking and behavior to develop creative and innovative skills. Soares (2002) conceptualizes it as a system that enables the creation and management of projects as vehicles for learning. Jones and English (2004) regard it as training

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to recognize business opportunities and act upon them. Tavares, Moura and Alves (2013) emphasize equipping students to make decisions and contribute to social development, seeking to strengthen their freedom of choice and prepare them for the future.

Leiva, Monge and Alegre (2014) position entrepreneurial education as part of the experiential learning process, influencing individuals' entrepreneurial behavior. Campos (2015) stresses the development of entrepreneurial skills and students' protagonism in overcoming challenges. Silva (2016) and Lopes (2017) discuss the development of entrepreneurial spirit and the transformation of creative ideas into action. Furthermore, entrepreneurial education is directly linked to students' personal development, assisting in defining personal projects and strengthening individual agency, as expressed by Dolabela (1999), Tavares, Moura and Alves (2013), and Campos (2015). This approach is also associated with the development of skills such as self-knowledge, self-esteem, perception, and critical thinking, as noted by Kirby and Ibrahim (2011), Jones and English (2004), and Carvalho (2022).

Oliveira, Melo and Muylder (2016) emphasize the importance of entrepreneurial education in preparing students to manage their own businesses and promote improvements that benefit society. Stockmanns (2016) highlights its role in raising awareness of individual strengths and weaknesses, while Johan, Kruger and Minello (2018) stress the practical and dynamic experiences provided by this form of education. According to Fayolle and Gailly (2006), entrepreneurial education is connected to concepts of management, business, and innovation, aiming to identify and articulate opportunities, create innovation and value, and address social and cultural issues in society, as discussed by a range of authors exploring these interconnections between entrepreneurial education and its economic, social, and cultural impact.

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From a methodological perspective, Silva (2018) highlights the teaching structure anchored in entrepreneurship as a way of adapting business management concepts to the educational environment. Neck and Corbett (2018) emphasize cognitive development and the skills necessary to initiate ventures as key elements of teaching methodology. Messias (2021) underscores entrepreneurial education's ability to develop qualities such as proactivity and confidence through active teaching methodologies. Rabelo (2021) and Carvalho (2022) broaden the perspective by considering that entrepreneurial education goes beyond business creation, focusing instead on professional and personal development, stimulating behavioral change, and fostering critical and ethical thinking.

PROPOSE METHOD

The methodological approach of this article is based on the framework proposed by Roesch (2015), being detailed in terms of its purpose, nature, design, and data collection and analysis techniques. Regarding its purpose, the research can be classified as basic, as it seeks knowledge as an end in itself (Roesch, 2015). This perspective aligns with the general objective of this study, since it analyzes publications on “entrepreneurial education” in the Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD).

In terms of its nature, the research can be classified as quantitative, as it transformed information from the selected theses into statistical data for analysis. The research design adopted for this study is descriptive research, which, according to Gil (2010), aims to describe the characteristics of a given population. In this study, the population consists of theses addressing the theme of “entrepreneurial education” that were selected for bibliographic analysis through the BDTD database. The technique used to collect data in this study was bibliographic research, which consists of obtaining information from already published secondary sources. According to Gil (2010), bibliographic research is

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conducted based on materials such as books, journals, newspapers, theses, dissertations, and proceedings of scientific events.

The data analysis technique adopted in this study was bibliometric analysis, which aims to ground the proposed research and achieve its objectives. This approach involves the use of statistical and mathematical techniques to describe aspects of the literature and other forms of communication (Araújo, 2006). According to Spinak (1996), bibliometrics represents a discipline dedicated to analyzing the scientific output related to the research theme, employing quantitative approaches in the study of production, dissemination, and use of recorded information through the application of mathematical and statistical methods. Araújo and Alvarenga (2011) point out that bibliometric investigation, through the collection, processing, and presentation of data, supports researchers in understanding the progress of knowledge in a given area of study or specific field.

For Sciasci et al. (2012), bibliometrics can be defined as “the study of the quantitative aspects of the production, dissemination, and use of recorded information, based on mathematical patterns and models”. Bastos and de Oliveira (2015) state that bibliometrics encompasses the quantification of bibliographic activities and enables the analysis of particular terms, such as authors, institutions, citation counts, and other aspects relevant to researchers.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The texts were selected through searches in the Google Scholar search tab for the topic "Entrepreneurial Education" between August 10 and 15, 2023. The search results then indicated 18 articles available in the Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDDT). These files were organized using Excel, revealing that one of them was duplicated. This resulted in a total of 17 texts for analysis based on the following dimensions: number of citations in

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Google Scholar, temporal evolution, type of publication, authorship, and keywords. Chart 1 presents the 17 theses selected and analyzed:

Chart 1: Theses on Entrepreneurial Education (2018-2023)

THESES	CITATIONS
SCHAEFER, R. Empreender como uma forma de ser, saber e fazer : O desenvolvimento da mentalidade e do comportamento empreendedores por meio da educação empreendedora. 2018. 281 f. Tese. Doutorado em administração (Programa de pós-graduação em administração). Universidade Federal de Santa Maria, 2018.	13
SILVA, H. B. Implantação de uma metodologia inovadora de ensino e avaliação para o desenvolvimento de competências empreendedoras : Um estudo de caso no curso de sistemas e mídias digitais da UFC. 2020. 192 f. Tese. Doutorado em educação (Programa de pós-graduação em educação brasileira). Universidade Federal do Ceará, 2020.	3
SOUZA, H. A. Educação empreendedora : Contribuições para a formação do perfil empreendedor de alunos da enfermagem. 2019. 265 f. Tese. Doutorado em administração (Programa de pós-graduação em enfermagem psiquiátrica). Universidade de São Paulo, 2019.	2
COPELLI, F. H. S. Empreendedorismo na pós-graduação em enfermagem : Tendências e significados. 2019. 132 f. Tese. Doutorado em enfermagem (Programa de pós-graduação em enfermagem). Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, 2019.	2
ZAMBON, S. A. O empreendedorismo e suas características comportamentais : uma análise da percepção da atitude empreendedora em teses publicadas no Brasil de 2007 a 2019. 2021. 274 f. Tese. Doutorado em ciência, tecnologia e sociedade (Programa de pós-graduação em ciência, tecnologia e sociedade). Universidade Federal de São Carlos, 2021.	2
SCHNEIDER, M. C. Protagonismo empreendedor : Uma forma singular de ensinar. 2020. 192 f. Tese. Doutorado em ensino na linha de pesquisa formação de professores, estudos do currículo e avaliação (Programa de pós-graduação stricto sensu). Universidade do Vale do Taquari, 2020.	1
ARAÚJO, G. F. Educação empreendedora pela ciência : Criatividade e emoção no contexto do empreendedorismo cultural. 2019. 226 f. Tese. Doutorado em administração (Núcleo de pós-graduação em administração). Universidade Federal da Bahia, 2019.	0
ARAÚJO, F. S. G. Modelagem de fatores capazes de influenciar a intenção empreendedora de estudantes de turismo . 2021. 207 f. Tese. Doutorado em turismo (Programa de pós-graduação em turismo). Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Norte, 2021.	0
MELLO, R. C. H. Percepções dos discentes do stricto sensu sobre a disciplina de empreendedorismo em sua formação como docente . 2022. 171 f. Tese. Doutorado em educação (Programa de pós-graduação em educação). Universidade Metodista de São Paulo, 2022.	0
FARINA, D. A. R. S. Entrepreneurship education through the lenses of entrepreneurial competences, intention, and confidence . 2021. 293 f. Tese. Doutorado em ciências (Programa de pós-graduação em engenharia de produção). Universidade de São Paulo, 2021.	0

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Chart 1: Theses on Entrepreneurial Education (2018-2023) - continuation

THESES	CITATIONS
RIBEIRO, A. T. V. B. Para além de grades curriculares : O valor das vivências formativas em empreendedorismo durante a graduação. 2021. 294 f. Tese. Doutorado em ciências (Programa de pós-graduação em administração). Universidade de São Paulo, 2021.	0
LEITE, R. C. Proposta de modelo de gestão da pesquisa inovativa para programas de pós-graduação . 2019. 132 f. Tese. Doutorado em biotecnologia (Programa de pós-graduação em biotecnologia). Universidade Federal de São Carlos, 2019.	0
SILVA, C. A. A. Ensino médio integrado no estado do Ceará : O empreendedorismo como perspectiva de formação para os jovens da escola pública. 2020. 163 f. Tese. Doutorado em educação (Programa de pós-graduação em educação brasileira). Universidade Federal do Ceará, 2020.	0
PAIVA, L. E. B. Intenção empreendedora, inovação e sustentabilidade : Uma abordagem cross-cultural. 2022. 204 f. Tese. Doutorado em administração e controladoria (Programa de pós-graduação em administração e controladoria). Universidade Federal do Ceará, 2022.	0
CUNHA, R. M. Criação e desenvolvimento de spin-offs no contexto da perspectiva emergente do empreendedorismo acadêmico . 2018. 177 f. Tese. Doutorado em engenharia de produção (Programa de pós-graduação em engenharia de produção). Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, 2018.	0
SILVA, J. P. Gestão educacional e interdisciplinaridade : A organização de um curso de empreendedorismo para a contemporaneidade. 2018. 78 f. Tese. Doutorado em educação (Programa de pós-graduação em educação). Universidade Católica de São Paulo, 2018.	0
ÁVILA, A. L. Emoção na educação empreendedora : A prática educacional do empreendedorismo artístico. 2022. 270 f. Tese. Doutorado em administração (Núcleo de pós-graduação em administração). Universidade Federal da Bahia, 2022.	0

Source: Research data (2024).

The theses were first analyzed according to their temporal evolution. Thus, the first texts were published in 2018 and were republished through 2022. Graph 1 shows the number of texts per year, as follows:

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Graph 1: Temporal evolution of theses on Entrepreneurial Education (2018-2023)

Source: Research data (2024).

Regarding the universities where the works were produced, it can be observed that four of them had more than one work thus representing approximately 58.82% of the total theses, as shown in graph 2.

Graph 2: Universities in theses on Entrepreneurial Education (2018-2023)

Source: Research data (2024).

Regarding the programs, a recurrence analysis was carried out, observing that there were a total of 12 different types of programs, as shown in graph 3.

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Graph 3: Programs in theses on Entrepreneurial Education (2018-2023)

Source: Research data (2024).

Regarding the base titles of each thesis, we analyzed their recurrences across the 17 papers and their citations on Google Scholar. Twenty-four distinct citations stood out, representing 67.30% of the entire database, totaling 291,614 citations. Finally, we analyzed 37 keywords from the 17 theses, resulting in a total of 52 entries. Some keywords were repeated, resulting in a total of 18 entries (34.62%), resulting in only three keywords with more than one recurrence, as shown in Graph 4.

Graph 4: Keywords in theses on Entrepreneurial Education (2018-2023)

Source: Research data (2024).

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FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The present research aimed to present a bibliographic portfolio addressing the theme of “entrepreneurial education”. The application of the study resulted in a total of 17 theses aligned with the researched theme and with recognized scientific relevance. Furthermore, the bibliometric analysis carried out highlighted, through this scientific journal, the temporal evolution of thesis publications on the subject over a five-year period (2018 to 2022), as well as the universities where the works were produced, the most prominent graduate programs, the recurrence of titles with a relevant number of citations, and the frequency of keywords cited in each thesis.

Thus, it was possible to observe, regarding temporal evolution, that the years 2019 and 2021 showed the highest peaks of publications, with a total of four works in each year. Concerning the universities where the theses were produced, the Federal University of Ceará (UFC) and the University of São Paulo (USP) stand out. As for graduate programs, the highlight goes to the graduate program in Administration, recurring across a total of 12 distinct programs. Another key factor for analysis relates to the recurrence of core titles referenced in each thesis, with 24 titles standing out, together representing 291,614 citations.

Keywords were also analyzed across the 17 theses. The most notable were education and innovation, each appearing eight times, thus ranking as the “leaders” in recurrence compared to the others. This research aims to contribute to the construction of knowledge through the development of a set of theoretical foundations related to the theme of “entrepreneurial education”, considering, in an unprecedented way, doctoral theses directed toward the subject. The theoretical knowledge in this area provides a relevant database, highlighting the importance of entrepreneurial education for socioeconomic development.

Although this study was structured with a certain rigor in the selection of theses and brought innovation compared to pre-existing research, there are

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limitations. Among the restrictions are: the search mechanism used for thesis selection, relying solely on the Google Scholar database, and the lack of scientific works that consider theses on this subject and could contribute to data collection and the establishment of a research methodology.

Thus, the following are suggested as contributions for future research: (i) exploration of other databases linked to the theme; (ii) periodic updating or replication of the survey process in order to remain up to date; (iii) a systemic application, referring to a research approach that considers the object of study holistically - that is, taking into account the interactions and interdependencies among the various elements that make up the system in question. In the research context, this implies adopting methods and practices that allow for a broader and more integrated understanding of the phenomenon under study.

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